

AN ACCURATE PREDICTION OF FAILURES IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING A LAYERWISE MODEL

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ABSTRACT

A nonlinear finite element progressive failure algorithm is presented where the Generalized Layerwise Plate Theory (GLPT) of Reddy is used for the kinematic description, and the material is modeled as a stable progressively fracturing solid. The geometric nonlinearity is taken into account in the von Kármán sense, and the extensibility of transverse normals is included in the finite element formulation. The stiffness reduction is carried out at the reduced integration Gauss points of the finite element mesh depending on the mode of failure. The progressive failure algorithm is used to study the effect of geometric nonlinearity, span-to-depth ratio, lamination sequence and the boundary conditions at the supports on the first-ply and the ultimate failure loads of composite laminates in bending.

Keywords: bending analysis, failure criteria, finite element analysis, first-ply failures, layerwise laminate theory, progressive failures, stiffness reduction, nonlinear analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite structures are subjected to a variety of loading conditions during their service life. An understanding of the response and failure of these structures for various loading conditions is necessary for the design of a safe structure. Considerable research has been done to understand the failure behavior of composite laminates subjected to inplane loading conditions such as tension, compression and shear. The failure behavior of composite laminates subjected to out-of-plane loads such as bending and twisting has not received as much attention as that of inplane loading. The failure analysis of composite laminates subjected to out-of-plane loads is complicated due to both material and geometric nonlinearities that come into play when the loads are increased beyond the first-ply failure. The material nonlinearity comes into picture due to damage in the form of matrix cracking, delamination and fiber breakage, and the geometric nonlinearity is due to the large displacements experienced by the structure before ultimate failure.

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In a progressive failure analysis, the effect of matrix cracking and other types of damage, such as delamination and fiber breakage, is taken into account in an average sense. It is based on the assumption that the damaged material could be replaced with an equivalent material of degraded properties. The properties of the damaged material are adjusted as the loading and progression of damage continues. Thus, the problem of conducting the stress analysis of a solid with voids and discontinuities is converted to that of a continuum consisting of layers of dissimilar materials.

The first attempt to model the failure behavior of composite laminates by progressive failure analysis was due to Petit and Waddoups [1]. They used the classical laminated plate theory (CLPT) for stress analysis and an incremental loading procedure for failure analysis. As a first step, the laminae tangent moduli in tension, compression, and inplane shear were obtained experimentally and these properties were stored as data in a pointwise manner. As the loading proceeds, the individual lamina tangent moduli were updated based on the stored data. Ultimate failure of a laminate was assumed to occur when the inplane laminate stiffness matrix $[A]$ becomes singular, or when a diagonal term of $[A]$ becomes negative. Sandhu, Sendekyj, and Gallo [2] followed a similar approach, where an energy criterion was used for failure prediction. The finite element method was used to solve the laminate problem, and the experimental stress-strain curves of lamina were represented as piecewise continuous cubic spline functions. Lamina failure was determined by using a total strain energy failure criterion, and the ply-discount method [3] was used for stiffness reduction.

Chang, Scott, and Springer [4-6] performed progressive failure analysis of notched composite laminates in tension and compression using the finite element model based on CLPT. The nonlinear stress-strain relation proposed by Hahn and Tsai [7] was used for inplane shear. Stiffness reduction was carried out at element level and a failure criterion originally proposed by Yamada and Sun [8] was used. Tan [9] included the effect of thermal residual stresses and hygroscopic stresses in his progressive failure model. The CLPT was used for stress analysis, and element stiffness property was taken as average value at the gauss points. The Tsai-Wu failure criterion was used for failure prediction.

It is clear from the above literature review that progressive failure analysis methods have been developed primarily for inplane loading and geometrically linear cases, where the CLPT is used for stress analysis (except by Averill and Reddy [10]). In the CLPT, the interlaminar stress fields are not represented accurately. However, it has been widely recognized that the interlaminar stress fields and the associated three-dimensional effects play an important role on the progression of failures in composite laminates [11,12]. Turvey [13], and Reddy and Reddy [14] have shown that the first-ply failure loads of composite laminates subjected to bending loads are extremely sensitive to the effect of geometric nonlinearity.

In the present study, the effect of geometric nonlinearity is studied both on the first-ply and the ultimate failure loads using the generalized layerwise plate theory (GLPT) of Reddy [15-18] and the first-order shear deformation plate theory (FSDT). Linear and nonlinear failure loads are computed for different lamination sequences, boundary conditions, and span-to-depth ratios of a three-point bending test specimen. The extensibility of transverse normals is included in GLPT. Because of this provision of transverse extensibility, the GLPT is able to capture the damage that takes place near the support. It is shown that the damage that takes place near the support has a profound influence on the failure behavior of composite laminates subjected to bending loads.

2. THE LAYERWISE MODEL

In the layerwise theory of Reddy [15-18], a piecewise continuous displacement field through the thickness is assumed. A detailed description of the GLPT and its finite element formulation for composite laminates without the von Kármán nonlinearity, can be

found in [17]. The basic premise of the Generalized Layerwise Plate Theory (GLPT) is that the displacement field can be expanded as,

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(x, y, z) &= \sum_{m=1}^N U_m(x, y) \phi_m(z) \\
 v(x, y, z) &= \sum_{m=1}^N V_m(x, y) \phi_m(z) \\
 w(x, y, z) &= \sum_{m=1}^N W_m(x, y) \phi_m(z)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where (u,v,w) are the displacement components along x, y, z directions, respectively, and N is the total number of nodes along z -direction. The functions $U_m(x, y)$, $V_m(x, y)$, $W_m(x, y)$ represent the inplane displacement field at the m -th interface of the composite laminate. The shape functions $\phi_m(z)$ are the 1-D Lagrangian interpolation functions along the z -direction. The expansion in (1) reduces the 3-D problem to a 2-D one in terms of the functions, (U_m, V_m, W_m). These functions are then approximated using two-dimensional finite elements. The equilibrium equations of the theory can be derived using the principle of virtual work.

$$\begin{bmatrix} [K_{smrk}^{11}] & [K_{smrk}^{12}] & [K_{smrk}^{13}] \\ [K_{smrk}^{21}] & [K_{smrk}^{22}] & [K_{smrk}^{23}] \\ [K_{smrk}^{31}] & [K_{smrk}^{32}] & [K_{smrk}^{33}] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \{U_{rk}\} \\ \{V_{rk}\} \\ \{W_{rk}\} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{F_{sm}^1\} \\ \{F_{sm}^2\} \\ \{F_{sm}^3\} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

where $\{U_{rk}\}$, $\{V_{rk}\}$, and $\{W_{rk}\}$ are the displacement components along the x, y , and z directions, respectively.

3. PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS AND STIFFNESS REDUCTION

The present progressive failure algorithm is based on the assumption that the material behaves like a stable progressively fracturing solid. This ideal material has the following properties (see [19]).

1. loses stiffness due to stable progressive fracture or damage during loading,
2. unloads in a linear elastic manner, and losses stiffness depending on the extent of progressive fracture or damage prior to unloading, and
3. has the property that the material may always be returned to a state of zero stress and strain by linear-elastic unloading.

For a material possessing the above properties, the direct stiffness matrix and the tangent stiffness matrix become one and the same. Therefore, the nonlinear iteration due to damage can be performed by the direct stiffness method.

Progressive failure analysis is based on the assumption that the damaged material could be substituted with an equivalent material of degraded properties. However, it is not an easy task to determine the degraded properties of the damaged material with certainty. In the present study the degraded properties are assumed to be a constant multiple of the original properties of the undamaged material. The constant which is to be determined experimentally, is called Stiffness Reduction Coefficient (SRC). When the value of SRC is known for a given lamination sequence, it is assumed that the same value of SRC holds good for any other lamination sequence as long as the same material system is maintained. The details of the stiffness reduction method are given below:

- (1) Compute the contribution of each stress component towards the failure index of the Tsai-Wu failure criterion and identify the stress component which contributes the maximum.
- (2) If the maximum is due to σ_1 , then the failure mode is fiber breakage. If the maximum value is due to σ_2 or σ_6 , then the failure mode is transverse cracking. If the maximum value is due to σ_3 or σ_4 or σ_5 , then the failure mode is delamination.
- (3) If the failure mode is fiber breakage, then $E_1, G_{13}, G_{12}, \nu_{13}$ and ν_{12} are degraded by multiplying with SRC.
- (4) If the failure mode is transverse cracking, then $E_2, G_{23}, G_{12}, \nu_{21}$ and ν_{23} are degraded by multiplying with SRC.
- (6) Appropriate logic is included in the computer code such that restrictions on elastic constants are maintained.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

The three-point bend test is chosen as an example problem. The geometry and other details of the problem are shown in Figure 1. Due to symmetry about the x and y axes, only one quarter of the test specimen is considered for finite element modeling. The support span and widths of all three test specimens considered for the first-ply and progressive failure analysis are the same: span=0.64 in. and width=1.0 in., stacking sequence=(0/0/0/0)_s; B:(90/90/90/90)_s, and C:(0/0/90/90)_s. The subscript 's' denotes symmetric laminate. The material properties of (T300/5208) graphite/epoxy pre-peg are: $E_1 = 19.2 \times 10^6$ psi, $E_2 = 1.56 \times 10^6$ psi, $E_3 = 1.56 \times 10^6$ psi, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 0.82 \times 10^6$ psi, $G_{23} = 0.49 \times 10^6$ psi, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.24$, $\nu_{23} = 0.49$, strengths, $X_T = 219.5 \times 10^3$ psi, $X_C = 246 \times 10^3$ psi, $Y_T = Z_T = 6.35 \times 10^3$ psi, $Y_C = Z_C = 23.85 \times 10^3$ psi, $R = 9.8 \times 10^3$ and $S = T = 12.6 \times 10^3$, and the ply thickness is 0.005 in.

Figure 1. Geometry and the finite element mesh used.

Two different boundary conditions are considered for the first-ply and progressive failure analysis. In the first case the laminate is assumed to slide freely on the supports in the x -direction, and in the second case the displacement u is restrained at the support. These boundary conditions are designated as BC1 and BC2 respectively. In the case of FSDT both

the u and w displacements are restrained at the midplane of the laminate, while in the case of GLPT they are restrained at the bottom surface of the laminate. However, along the axes of symmetry the displacements are restrained throughout the thickness.

First-ply and progressive failure loads are computed for different lamination sequences. Both linear and nonlinear failure loads are computed by using the Tsai–Wu failure criterion. The finite element models based on both the First Order Shear Deformation Theory (FSDT) and the Generalized Layerwise Plate Theory (GLPT) are used. The Newton–Raphson iteration procedure is used to solve the nonlinear algebraic equations. Due to the space limitation, only results for the ratio $S/d = 16$ and boundary conditions BC1 are included here. However, the observations based on two different ratios of S/d and boundary conditions will be discussed in the section on conclusions.

Reduced integration is used to evaluate all the transverse stiffness terms, and full integration is used to evaluate all other stiffness terms in the case of FSDT. However, this type of selective reduced integration is not desirable in the case of GLPT, because it gives rise to spurious energy modes and abnormal out-of-plane deflections (see [17]). Therefore, full integration is used throughout in the case of GLPT.

The stresses are computed at the reduced integration Gauss points. However, in the case of transverse loading the maximum normal stress occurs always at the top and bottom surfaces of the laminate. Therefore, the Gauss point stresses are extrapolated to the corner nodes of the finite element before applying the failure criterion, and the stiffness properties are reduced at the corner nodes. These nodal stiffness properties are again interpolated to obtain the stiffness properties at the Gauss points to compute the direct and tangent stiffness matrices. Linear Lagrange interpolation functions are used to interpolate the stiffness properties. It is not desirable to use quadratic interpolation or extrapolation functions, because when the stiffness property at the center nodes is made equal to zero, there is a possibility of the stiffness properties getting negative in between the nodes.

The finite element mesh used in the progressive failure analysis is shown in Figure 1. A refined mesh is used near the support and at the middle of the test specimen, where the uniformly distributed line load is applied. The number of elements along the x axis are chosen to be 6, after conducting a convergence study for a fixed number of elements along the y and z axes (1 and 4 respectively).

4.2 First-Ply Failure Analysis

The first-ply failure analysis is based on the assumption that a given ply would fail when the failure index at any point within the ply reaches a value of unity. The failure index is defined as $F_i\sigma_i + F_{ij}\sigma_{ij}$, where F_i and F_{ij} are the coefficients in the polynomial failure criterion (see [14]). The computation of the first-ply failure load for the nonlinear formulation requires an iterative procedure. The maximum failure index is determined by carrying out a sequential search at certain chosen points within the laminte.

The laminate failure is checked by comparing the absolute value of (maximum failure index - 1) with a predetermined value of maximum tolerable error, ϵ . In the present study the value of ϵ is chosen to be 0.01. For the linear failure analysis the initial load is chosen to be unity and for the nonlinear failure analysis the initial load is chosen to be the linear failure load. At the end of each iteration, the initial load for the next iteration is computed as,

$$\text{Initial load for the next iteration} = (\text{Initial load of current iteration}) (\lambda)$$

where λ is a multiplication factor to be computed as below:

For the independent failure criteria λ is given as

$$\lambda = 1/(\text{Maximum failure index})$$

For the polynomial failure criteria λ is obtained by

$$\lambda^2(F_i\sigma_i\sigma_j) + \lambda(F_i\sigma_i) - 1 = 0$$

The real and smaller value of λ obtained from the above equation is used to compute the initial load for the next iteration. The results of the first-ply failure analysis are discussed next.

Figure 2. Comparison of linear and nonlinear *first-ply* failure loads as predicted by FSDT and GLPT for different laminates.

Figure 3. Comparison of linear and nonlinear *ultimate* failure loads as predicted by FSDT and GLPT for different laminates.

Figure 2 shows the results of first-ply failure analysis for an S/d ratio of 16 and BC1. The linear and nonlinear loads are found to be almost the same in this case. This is due to

the small S/d ratio. The failure loads predicted by the GLPT are much smaller than those of FSDT in the case of laminates A and C. Because, the loads are not corresponding to the same failure mode and locations. In the case of FSDT the failure took place at the center of the span and is due to σ_1 for laminate A and due to σ_2 for laminate C. Whereas, in the case of GLPT the failure took place at the support of the span and is due to the transverse normal stress (σ_3) for both laminates. The FSDT is not able to capture the damage at the support, because the transverse normals are assumed to be inextensible in that case. On the other hand, the extensibility of transverse normals is included in the GLPT, and therefore, it is able to capture the transverse normal stress (σ_3) and the damage at the support.

4.3 Progressive Failure Analysis

In the case of progressive failure analysis, the stiffness reduction is carried out only after the displacement has converged at a given load increment. The progressive (ultimate) failure loads in the nonlinear failure analysis are found to be very sensitive to the load increment size. A large load step would make the specimen excessively stiff due to the effect of geometric nonlinearity and a small step size would make the specimen too compliant due to the effect of damage. In the present study a load increment size of approximately 5% of the first-ply failure load and a Stiffness Reduction Coefficient (SRC) of 10^{-6} are used. The results of the progressive failure analysis are discussed below:

Figure 3 shows the results of progressive failure analysis for an S/d ratio of 16 and BC1. The results show that there is large difference between the first-ply and ultimate failure loads as predicted by GLPT. Whereas, in the case of FSDT the difference is considerably less. This is because of the fact that in the case of FSDT both first-ply failure and the progression of damage take place at the midspan, while GLPT predicts first-ply failure at the support and progression of failure both at the support and at the midspan. It is also interesting to note that the nonlinear failure loads predicted by GLPT are less than the linear failure loads. This is due to the fact that the nonlinear failure analysis predicts more damage at the support than the linear failure analysis. However, this is not true in the case of laminate B, because for this laminate progression of damage takes place only at the midspan.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Linear and nonlinear (von-Kármán), first-ply and progressive (ultimate) failure loads are computed for various lamination sequences, span-to-depth ratios and boundary conditions at the support. The effect of extensibility of transverse normals is included in the GLPT and the predictions of GLPT are compared with those of FSDT. It is demonstrated that the effect of geometric nonlinearity is more pronounced for those laminates with large span-to-depth ratios (results not shown here), which undergo more damage at the midspan than at the support. With regard to the boundary conditions, those laminates which are not allowed to slide on the supports (BC2) (results not shown here) are found to be more sensitive to the effect of geometric nonlinearity than those which slide on the support (BC1). The predictions of GLPT are shown to be qualitatively different from those of FSDT. The study shows that the damage that takes place near the support due to the transverse normal stress (σ_3) has a profound influence on the failure behavior of composite laminates in bending.

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